

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O‘RTA
MAXSUS TA’LIM VAZIRLIGI**
**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI INNOVATSION
RIVOJLANISH VAZIRLIGI**
**TERMIZ MUHANDISLIK-TEKNOLOGIYA
INSTITUTI**

**“FAN, TA’LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA
MUHANDISLIK-TEKNOLOGIYA SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI”
MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO TALABALAR ANJUMANI
2022-YIL 30-NOYABR**

**“PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGICAL FIELD BASED ON THE INTEGRATION
OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION”
NOVEMBER 30, 2022**

**МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ СТУДЕНЧЕСКАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ НА ТЕМУ
«ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНЖЕНЕРНО-ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ
ОБЛАСТИ, ОСНОВАННОЙ НА ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАУКИ,
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ПРОИЗВОДСТВА»
30 НОЯБРЯ 2022 ГОДА**

II-QISM

REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
MINISTRY OF HIGHER
AND SECONDARY SPECIAL EDUCATION

TERMEZ INSTITUTE
OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

« PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENGINEERING-
TECHNOLOGY FIELD ON THE BASE OF THE INTEGRATION OF
SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION »

CERTIFICATE

at the International Student Conference for active participation
presented to Mikhaylov Aleksandr Borisovich

on 29 and 30th november, 2022 y.

Rector U.AKHMEDOV

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Termiz-2022

Ushbu ilmiy ishlar to'plamida Xalqaro hamda Respublika oliy ta'lim muassasasalari va ilmiy-tadqiqot institutlari hamda Termiz muhandislik-texnologiya institutida faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan professor-o'qituvchi va talabalarning ilmiy ish natijalari e'lon qilingan. Anjuman materiallari Termiz muhandislik-texnologiya instituti Kengashining qarori asosida nashrga tavsiya etildi (Bayonnoma №-4 2022-yil noyabr).

Mas'ul muharrir:

O'.Axmedov –Termiz muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori;

Tahrir hay'ati:

1. M.Urozov – Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektor;
2. B.Amanov – Ilmiy-tadqiqotlar, innovatsiyalar va ilmiy-pedagogik kadrlar tayyorlash bo'limi boshlig'i;
3. M.Kichkilova – Iqtidorli talabalarning ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etish bo'limi boshlig'i;
4. H.Jumaev – Ilmiy innovatsion ishlanmalarni tijoratlashtirish bo'limi boshlig'i;
5. Sh.Chorshanbiev – Xalqaro aloqalar bo'limi boshlig'i;
6. F.Eshqurbonov – Yengil sanoat va kimyo texnologiyalari fakulteti dekani;
7. B.Xushboqov – Energetika va transport tizimlari fakulteti dekani;
8. B.Primqulov – Mexanika fakulteti dekani.

To'plamda chop etilgan ma'lumotlar va raqamlar mualliflar tomonidan taqdim etilgan. Nashriyot va tashkiliy qo'mita chop etilgan ma'lumotlar uchun mas'uliyatni o'z zimmasiga olmaydi.

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM

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Artificial intelligence is widely used in many areas of human life: in household appliances, "smart" electronics, financial management, data analysis, programming [1]. Economic entities have a need to use this tool to maintain competitiveness and develop their subsystems, which encourages states to join the technological race in order to stimulate the economy, strengthen their geopolitical positions, and improve the living standards of the population.

Artificial intelligence is a specific field of computer science engaged in the development of intelligent computer systems with capabilities that are traditionally associated with the human mind: the ability to understand language, learning, reasoning, solving all kinds of tasks and problems.

John McCarthy, the author of the term "artificial intelligence" defined the intellectual function as a computational component of the ability to achieve goals. Back in the middle of the last century, scientists were trying to understand how the human brain works. Then there were theories of computing, theories of algorithms and the first computers in the world, the computing capabilities of which prompted the luminaries of science to think about whether a machine could be compared with a human mind. The solution to this question was a test created by the English mathematician Alan Turing, which determines whether a machine can think [2].

It should be noted that the financial and economic sphere of any state that is highly developed in terms of information and intellectual technologies traditionally relies not only on vast arrays of data, but also on the possibility of their optimal and high-precision processing; it is for this reason that the introduction of artificial intelligence is quite natural and expected for the financial and economic sector.

The introduction of artificial intelligence and automation technologies can do a lot to boost the global economy and increase global prosperity. In a period of aging and falling fertility, productivity growth becomes critical for long-term economic growth. Even in the short term, labor productivity growth is declining by an average of 0.5% [3]. Like previous general-purpose technologies, artificial intelligence can contribute to productivity growth. Artificial intelligence will also create positive externalities, facilitating more efficient cross-border trade and expanding opportunities for the use of valuable cross-border data flows. Such an increase in economic activity and income can be reinvested in the economy, contributing to further growth.

Overall, these various channels lead to significant positive economic growth, assuming that businesses and governments will actively manage the transition process. According to McKinsey research, the use of artificial intelligence can increase global GDP by \$13 trillion by 2030, with an additional increase of 1.2% per year. However, this effect will only increase over time, given that most of the implementation costs may outpace the revenue potential [4].

An example of investing in the field of new technologies can serve as the largest transaction in history related to artificial intelligence. One of the most influential rating agencies in the world, S&P Global, acquires Kensho, a company engaged in developments in the field of artificial intelligence for a fabulous \$ 550 million. As already noted, artificial intelligence has become a new milestone in the development of financial statistics, and in order to get Kensho, a pioneer in this field, S&P is ready to pay a generous price. This is more expensive than the takeover of the startup DeepMind Technologies by the search giant Google, or the purchase of Nervana Systems by Intel Corporation, not to mention similar deals from Apple and Twitter. Initially, Kensho was conceived as a special tool using machine learning in order to carry out complex analysis of financial data as simply as a Google search. The startup owner created an algorithm called Warren (in honor of

Warren Buffett), which found matches and correlations among millions of different indicators and offered potentially profitable deals.

The potential benefits of artificial intelligence for business and the global financial and economic system, as well as how technology solves some social problems, should encourage business leaders and those who determine the state of the economy to adopt new technologies. At the same time, the potential problems associated with their implementation, including the impact on the workforce and other social problems, cannot be ignored.

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Olimova O.S.

Farg'ona politexnika instituti

Zamonaviy raqamli olamda raqamli dunyo tahdidlaridan ishonchli himoya asosiy ehtiyojga aylanmoqda. Xakerlar oddiy fuqarolarning bank hisoblarini bo'shatishmoqda va shuning uchun ham kiberxavfsizlikka bo'lgan ehtiyoj o'sib bormoqda. Har bir shaxs kiberxavfsizlik nima ekanligini va nima uchun bu haqdagi bilimlarga ega bo'lishi lozimligini izohlash zarur deb o'ylaymiz.

Kiberxavfsizlik - bu Internetga ulangan tizimlarni kiber tahdidlardan himoya qilish.

Ko'pincha "kiberxavfsizlik" va "axborot xavfsizligi" atamalariga bir hil tushunchalar sifatida qaraladi. Biroq, aslida, bu atamalar juda farq qiladi va bir-birini almashtirib bo'lmaydi. Kiberxavfsizlik kibermakondagi hujumlardan himoyalaniшни nazarda tutsa, axborot xavfsizligi esa xoh analog, xoh raqamli shakldagi ma'lumotlarni har qanday tahdidlardan himoya qilishni nazarda tutadi.

Kiberxavfsizlik amaliyoti turli sohalarda - sanoat korxonalaridan tortib oddiy foydalanuvchilarning mobil qurilmalarigacha qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kiberxavfsizlik texnologiyalari va ilg'or amaliyotlar muhim tizimlar va nozik ma'lumotlarni tez o'sib borayotgan murakkab kiberhujumlardan himoya qiladi.

Hozirgi kunda zamonaviy kiberxavfsizlik tahdidlarning quyidagi asosiy turlari bilan kurashmoqda:

Zararli dasturiy ta'minot (ZDT). Kompyuter, tarmoq yoki serverga zarar etkazadigan har qanday dastur yoki fayl. Zararli dasturlarga kompyuter viruslari, qurtlar, troyan otlari, ransomware va josuslik dasturlari kiradi. Zararli dastur nozik ma'lumotlarni o'g'irlyaydi, shifrlaydi va o'chiradi, asosiy hisoblash funksiyalarini o'zgartiradi yoki o'g'irlyaydi hamda kompyuter yoki ilovalar faoliyatini nazorat qiladi.

Ijtimoiy muhandislik. Odamlarning o'zaro ta'siriga asoslangan hujum usuli. Jinoyatchilar foydalanuvchilarga o'zlarini qiziqtiradilar va ularni xavfsizlik tartib-qoidalarini buzishga, maxfiy ma'lumotlarni berishga majbur qiladi.

Fishing. Ijtimoiy muhandislikning bir shakli. Firibgarlar foydalanuvchilarga ishonchli manbalardan kelgan xabarlarga o'xshash elektron pochta yoki matnli xabarlar yuboradi. Ommaviy

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